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Strengthening interpersonal relationships through social skills: evidence and application

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Strengthening interpersonal relationships is an essential aspect of promoting enriching human interactions based on effective communication, mutual trust and collaboration. In this context, social skills play a central role, particularly active listening, empathy, assertiveness, emotional management and conflict resolution. These skills are fundamental to building strong and healthy relationships in various contexts, such as the workplace, the family and educational institutions.

Theoretically, strengthening interpersonal relationships is based on widely recognized models. Emotional Intelligence Theory stresses the importance of understanding and managing one's own and others' emotions (Goleman, 1995). Social Learning Theory emphasizes the role of observation and practice in learning social behaviors (Bandura, 1977). Social Exchange Theory understands relationships as exchanges of costs and rewards, highlighting reciprocity as an essential element (Thibaut & Kelley, 1959).

Empirical studies reinforce the connection between social skills and interpersonal benefits. In work environments, these skills are associated with higher productivity, improved organizational climate and reduced staff turnover (Cantero-Sánchez et al., 2021). In the educational context, they favor a more positive environment and have a direct impact on academic performance (Durlak et al., 2022). In families, they contribute to reducing conflicts and strengthening cohesion (Esteves Villanueva et al., 2020).

An innovative aspect addressed is the use of new technologies, such as virtual reality and metaverse, in social skills training. These technologies offer immersive and controlled environments in which individuals can practice and develop interpersonal skills in a safe and realistic manner. Among these initiatives is the Carmides Metaverse, developed by the University of Seville, which integrates interactive simulations aimed at improving social skills, especially in healthcare professionals (García Jiménez et al., 2023; León Rubio et al., 2022). This platform allows participants to experience challenging situations, receive real-time feedback and gradually improve their competencies through a highly engaging experience.

These technologies also offer the opportunity to customize interventions based on the specific needs of individuals or groups. The combination of simulated scenarios and the possibility of repeating real situations in controlled environments facilitates the consolidation of learning, while reducing the impact of errors during the training process.

Another relevant differential in the study of interpersonal relationships is the integration of biochemical and neurophysiological indicators to assess the impact of social interactions on physical and emotional well-being. Among the most prominent biomarkers are:

- **Oxytocin:** Known as the “attachment hormone,” it is released in positive social interactions, such as displays of affection and trust. Its presence is associated with increased empathy, cooperation and stress reduction, providing an objective physiological indicator of the quality of interpersonal relationships (e.g., Feldman, 2012; Soporta-Wiesel et al., 2024).
- **Heart rate variability (HRV):** this marker reflects autonomic nervous system activity and is related to the ability to regulate emotional stress. Positive interpersonal relationships increase HRV, while conflictual interactions tend to reduce it. This metric is especially useful for monitoring interventions aimed at strengthening interpersonal bonds (e.g., Thayer et al., 2012; Volper-Esmond et al., 2024).
- **Cortisol:** Cortisol is a stress-related hormone, and its levels increase in situations of conflict or interpersonal stress. Improved interpersonal relationships may decrease activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, reducing cortisol release. Quality interpersonal relationships, characterized by social support, have been shown to reduce cortisol levels during stressful situations. Cohen & Janicki-Deverts (2009) showed that people with larger and higher quality social support networks have lower cortisol responses to stress.
- **Serotonin:** This neurotransmitter is involved in mood regulation and emotional well-being. Satisfying interpersonal relationships can influence serotonin levels, helping to improve mood and reduce symptoms of depression and anxiety. Studies suggest that positive social interactions and social support can influence the serotonergic system. For example, Young (2007) explored how bonding and social well-being are related to serotonin balance, which influences emotional stability.
- **Endorphins:** Endorphins are neurotransmitters associated with reduced pain and increased pleasure. Positive social bonds, such as physical contact and emotional support, are associated with endorphin release, which contributes to emotional and physical well-being. For example, Dunbar (2012) proposed the “Social Endorphin Hypothesis,” suggesting that social interactions, such as laughter and physical contact, trigger the release of endorphins, thereby strengthening social bonds and improving well-being.
- **Inflammatory markers:** Conflictual or low-quality interpersonal relationships have been associated with higher levels of inflammatory markers, such as C-reactive protein (CRP) and tumor necrosis factor (TNF- α). In contrast, positive interpersonal relationships and social support networks can reduce these inflammatory markers, suggesting a protective effect on physical and mental health. For example, Kiecolt-Glaser et al. (2010) found that couples with conflictual relationships showed higher levels of inflammatory markers, while those with more harmonious relationships exhibited lower levels of inflammation.
- **Amygdala activity:** The amygdala is a key brain region in the processing of emotions, especially fear and anxiety. Supportive interpersonal relationships can reduce amygdala hyperactivity in response to stressful stimuli, aiding better emotional regulation. A study by Eisenberger et al. (2007) showed that people who felt socially supported had lower amygdala activation in situations of social stress, suggesting that social support buffers the negative emotional response.

In summary, research suggests that improved interpersonal relationships not only have positive psychological effects, but also impact a wide range of neurophysiological and biochemical indicators. Oxytocin, cortisol, heart rate variability, endorphins, inflammatory markers, and amygdala activity are some of the markers that show how social relationships affect our biology, confirming that quality interpersonal relationships are fundamental to holistic health and well-being.

The application of social skills training (SST) programs, emotional intelligence workshops and the use of technologies such as virtual reality and metaverse have demonstrated their effectiveness in various contexts. However, the implementation of these initiatives faces challenges such as resistance to change, limited resources and difficulties in generalizing the skills learned beyond the training environment. To overcome these barriers, it is essential to involve leaders, continuously monitor interventions and use technologies that allow training strategies to be customized.

Strengthening interpersonal relationships therefore requires a multifaceted approach that combines soft skills development, new technologies and biometric measurements. The integration of innovative tools, such as the Metaverse Carmenides, and the incorporation of physiological indicators expand the ability to assess and promote healthier, more effective and sustainable human interactions. These strategies offer promising avenues for strengthening interpersonal bonds, both professionally and personally.

References

- Bandura, A. (1977). *Social Learning Theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Cohen S, Janicki-Deverts D. (2009) Can we improve our physical health by altering our social networks? *Perspect Psychol Sci.* (4):375-378.
- Dunbar R.I. (2012). Bridging the bonding gap: the transition from primates to humans. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci.* 367(1597):1837-46. doi: 10.1098/rstb.2011.0217.
- Durlak, J. A., Mahoney, J. L., & Boyle, A. E. (2022). What we know, and what we need to find out about universal, school-based social and emotional learning programs for children and adolescents: A review of meta-analyses and directions for future research. *Psychological Bulletin*, 148(11-12), 765–782.
- Eisenberger NI, Taylor SE, Gable SL, Hilmert CJ, Lieberman MD. (2007). Neural pathways link social support to attenuated neuroendocrine stress responses. *Neuroimage.* 35(4):1601-12. doi: 10.1016/j.neuroimage.2007.01.038.
- Esteves Villanueva, A. R., Paredes Mamani, R. P., Calcina Condori, C. R., & Yapuchura Saico, C. R.. (2020). Habilidades Sociales en adolescentes y Funcionalidad Familiar. *Comuni@cción*, 11(1), 16-27.
- Feldman, R. (2012). Oxytocin and social affiliation in humans. *Hormones and Behavior*, 61(3), 380-391.
- García Jiménez, F.; León-Rubio, J.M.; León-Pérez, J.M.; González Alonso, J.; Molina-Capilla, M.; Cárdenas de la Miyar, A. y Canseco Fernández, A. (2023). Presentación del metaverso del servicio de recursos audiovisuales y nuevas tecnologías. Introducción al mundo cármides. Universidad de Sevilla. Disponible en: https://tv.us.es/media/1_0512u00r
- Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ*. New York: Bantam Books.
- Kiecolt-Glaser JK, Gouin JP, Hantsoo L. (2010). Close relationships, inflammation, and health. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev.* 35(1):33-8. doi: 10.1016/j.neubiorev.2009.09.003.
- León Rubio, J. M., León Pérez, J. M., Cantero Sánchez, F. J., Vázquez-Morejón, R., Garrido Torres, M. Á., Bueno Moreno, R.,... Sobrino Toro, J. P. (2022). Metaverso sobre habilidades sociales Cármides Sevilla, Secretariado de Recursos Audiovisuales y Nuevas Tecnologías de la Universidad de Sevilla.

- Saporta-Wiesel, L., Feldman, R., Levi, L., Davidson, M., Burshtein, S., Gur, R., Zagoory-Sharon, O., Amiaz, R., Park, J., Davis, J. M., & Weiser, M. (2024). Intranasal Oxytocin Combined with Social Skills Training for Schizophrenia: an add-on Randomized Controlled Trial. *Schizophrenia Bulletin Open*.
- Thayer, J. F., Ahs, F., Fredrikson, M., Sollers, J. J., & Wager, T. D. (2012). A meta-analysis of heart rate variability and neuroimaging studies: Implications for heart rate variability as a marker of stress and health. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 36(2), 747-756.
- Thibaut, J. W., & Kelley, H. H. (1959). *The Social Psychology of Groups*. New York: Wiley.
- Volpert-Esmond, H. I., Bray, J. R., Pages, S. M., & Danyluck, C. (2024). Cardiovascular reactivity during conversations about discrimination is buffered by social support among U.S. Latines. *Scientific reports*, 14(1), 26964. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-76795-y>
- Young S.N. (2007). How to increase serotonin in the human brain without drugs. *J Psychiatry Neurosci.*;32(6):394-9. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2077351/>